

Assessing the impact of cornering losses on the energy consumption of electric city buses

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ABSTRACT

In view of the increasing electrification of public city transport, an accurate energy consumption prediction for Battery Electric Buses (BEBs) is essential. Conventional prediction algorithms do not consider energy losses that occur during turning of the vehicle. This is especially relevant for electric city buses, which have a limited battery capacity and often drive curvy routes.

In this paper, the additional energy consumption during steering of a BEB is modeled, measured, and assessed. A nonlinear steady-state cornering model is developed to establish the additional energy losses during cornering. The model includes large steer angles, load transfer, and a Magic Formula tire model. Model results show that both *cornering resistance* and *tire scrub* of the rear tires cause additional energy losses during cornering, depending on the corner radius and vehicle velocity.

The energy consumption model is validated with full scale vehicle tests and shows an average deviation of 0.8kW compared to the measurements. Analysis of recorded real-world bus routes reveals that on average these effects constitute 3.1% of the total powertrain energy. The effect is even more significant for routes crossing city centers, reaching values up to 5.8%. In these cases, cornering losses can be significant and should not be neglected in an accurate energy consumption prediction.

1. Introduction

In the recent transition towards electric mobility, Battery Electric Buses (BEBs) are one of the first public transport solutions deployed on a large scale in many city centers (ZeEUS, 2016; Du et al., 2019). BEBs offer the advantage of zero local emissions and a possibility for a reduced total cost of ownership, due to the relatively low operational expenses (Pihlatie et al., 2014).

Even though the electric drives of BEBs are more energy efficient than the internal combustion engines of conventional vehicles, the available energy stored in the vehicle is rather limited. This is mainly a consequence of the energy density of batteries still being low compared to fossil fuels (Ding et al., 2019). Also, there is often little space available for batteries, as using maximum space for passengers still has priority. As a result, most current BEBs have a limited driving range. Moreover, the driving range can vary depending on several environmental and vehicle conditions, such as usage of vehicle auxiliaries, vehicle mass, and road conditions (Asamer et al., 2016). Practise shows that these effects result in conservative time table scheduling and use of redundant vehicles, and consequently in an increased total cost of ownership.

To mitigate the problems posed by the limited and uncertain driving range of BEBs, energy consumption prediction methods are discussed extensively in literature. The proposed models can be subdivided into physics-based methods (Wang et al., 2017;

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Vepsäläinen et al., 2018; Sarrafan et al., 2017) and data-driven methods (Shankar and Marco, 2013; De Cauwer et al., 2015). Most models consider a multitude of dependent variables, ranging from road slope and road roughness, to losses of individual powertrain components, and detailed weather information. However, a common assumption in most of these methods is that the vehicle is driving in a straight line, i.e., only the longitudinal vehicle dynamics are accounted for. This is not necessarily true, especially when city buses are considered. The city routes contain many corners, which potentially cause additional tire wear and energy losses. The goal of this paper is to model, measure, and assess the energy losses that occur in the tires when cornering a BEB.

1.1. State-of-the-art

There are some energy consumption prediction studies that consider the influence of corners. For example Ojeda et al. (2017), who successfully identified the curves and roundabouts along a route and included these in the speed profile generation for heavy-duty trucks. However, the vehicle dynamic model that is used to predict energy consumption neglects the effects of tire slip.

Early research indicates that additional energy losses occur in the tires of road vehicles during cornering. This was modeled by Hales (1977) and later experimentally confirmed by Gyenes et al. (1979). Both studies focus on heavy-duty articulated vehicles and recognize that lateral tire forces result in additional resistance during cornering, which in later research is referred to as *cornering resistance*. Gyenes et al. (1979) estimate that a maximum of 3% of the total fuel consumption of long haul articulated freight trucks can be ascribed to this effect.

There are several studies that recognize the relevance of cornering losses, and aim to minimize these through the development of vehicle dynamic models and application of control. An exemplary study is (Kobayashi et al., 2017), where a linear bicycle model is used to find an expression for the total power required to corner a vehicle. The validated model is used to develop a control strategy that minimizes the cornering resistance by yaw moment control. Likewise, Ikezawa et al. (2019) use a linear bicycle model to find an explicit expression for the cornering resistance force. This resistance is included in the total energy losses, which are minimized through optimization of the velocity profile under time constraints. A bicycle model with linear tire forces is also used in (Bhat et al., 2017) to explore various ways to minimize the power required for cornering an over-actuated vehicle. The model is later extended to a double-track model with nonlinear tire forces to expose the potential of active camber control (Sun et al., 2018). This model then is extended to a full six degree of freedom model, including body roll, to investigate the possible energy savings of rear axle steering and torque vectoring (Edrén et al., 2019). The extension towards more complex models enables an accurate description of the nonlinear dynamics a vehicle might experience in tight cornering situations.

There are further studies that use more complex double-track models to describe the nonlinear dynamics that occur during cornering and relate these to energy losses. Maclaurin (2008) analyses the steering characteristics of a heavy-duty six wheeled military vehicle. The author uses a steady-state double-track cornering model of the vehicle to compare different steering geometries, also taking energy consumption into account. In (Rill, 2017), a double-track model with load transfer is used for the development of a computationally-efficient control strategy to minimize cornering resistance. Lastly, in (Chatzikomis et al., 2019), an energy efficient torque vectoring control strategy is developed, also taking into account the energy efficiency of the individual electric motors. The cornering resistance is calculated using the IPG Carmaker model. This model is detailed more extensively in (De Novellis et al., 2014) and includes several nonlinear effects, such as large angle assumptions and weight transfer.

This brief survey reveals that the energy losses in the tires due to cornering are acknowledged in literature. Models of varying complexity are used to describe these effects. Even though some models manage to describe the elaborate nonlinear dynamics involved in a cornering a road vehicle, many studies still use linear models without load transfer. Moreover, only few of the described studies validate the energy consumption predicted by the models. While the models are mostly used to minimize the energy consumption through control, only little effort is focussed on the impact of these losses on the total energy consumption. The contribution of the cornering losses has not yet been compared to the total energy consumption in a range prediction context. Finally, little of the cornering related research is focussed on city buses, which drive curvy routes, often have double mounted tires, and have a high center of gravity.

1.2. Contribution

This paper assesses the impact of the energy losses experienced by battery electric buses during cornering. Hereto, a nonlinear double-track steady-state cornering model is used. The model includes double tires on the rear axle to resemble the lay-out of a two-axle, 12 meter city bus without articulation. Furthermore, it includes relevant dynamic effects, such as nonlinear tire forces, longitudinal and lateral load transfer, and large steer angles. Two effects that contribute to the energy consumption are considered: *cornering resistance* and *tire scrub*.

Novelty of this work can be found in the fact that the model is validated on an energy consumption level by comparing it to the results of full-scale steady-state cornering tests. The energy-level validation and the inclusion of load transfer effects, make the model suitable to assess the cornering losses for electric city buses. Additionally, 62 h of recorded real-world vehicle data from multiple routes are used to establish the relative impact of the cornering losses on the measured total energy consumption of the vehicles.

The outline of this paper is as follows. In Section 2, the nonlinear double-track steady-state cornering model of a BEB is presented. The model is used to calculate the cornering losses for a typical BEB. Next, in Section 3, the model is validated with results from experiments. In Section 4, the validated model is applied to a set of recorded real-world electric bus routes to establish the significance of cornering losses. A discussion of the results is provided in Section 5 and the conclusions are given in Section 6.

Fig. 1. Schematic view of the steady-state cornering model. The tire locations are defined by the dimensions l_f , l_r , s_1 , s_2 , and Δs . The positive definitions of the velocity vector \vec{v}_i , the longitudinal force $\vec{F}_{x,i}$, the lateral force $\vec{F}_{y,i}$, and the side-slip angle α_i are indicated for each of the six tires ($i = 1, \dots, 6$). In the CoG, a vehicle fixed axis system (\vec{e}_x, \vec{e}_y) is located. The normal acceleration vector is indicated with \vec{a}_n .

2. Nonlinear double-track steady-state cornering model

A vehicle dynamic double-track model is developed with the goal of accurately identifying the tire forces and resulting energy losses during cornering of a BEB. The model is presented first in (Beckers et al., 2019) and is recapped here to make this work self-contained. Throughout the model description, a multibody dynamics approach is used to easily add additional tires to a standard double-track model, thereby simulating double tires on the rear axle. Furthermore, the model includes longitudinal and lateral load transfer caused by the elevated center of the gravity of the vehicle. Angles are assumed to be large and the tire forces are represented by Pacejka’s Magic Formula (Pacejka, 2012). As a consequence, the four equations of motion resulting from the model are highly nonlinear. Therefore, a steady-state solution is found using Newton iterations. The complete code for the model presented in this section is publicly available in (Beckers et al., 2020). Data related to the experimental validation in Section 3 and to the route analysis in Section 4 are not included, because these are subject to a confidentiality agreement.

A schematic top view of a BEB is displayed in Fig. 1. The figure shows relevant dimensions, individual tire velocity vectors, and tire force vectors. The tires at each side of the rear axle are assumed to have the same angular velocity, i.e., tires 3 and 4 rotate at a speed ω_L and tires 5 and 6 at a speed ω_R . The figure depicts a steady-state cornering situation. This implies that both the vehicle velocity $v = |\vec{v}|$ and the cornering radius R are constant. The vehicle’s left and right front wheels are steered and have individual steer angles δ_1 and δ_2 respectively, which are also constant. An average steer angle is defined as $\delta = \frac{1}{2}(\delta_1 + \delta_2)$. Furthermore, the vehicle has a constant yaw-rate ω_z , a constant vehicle side-slip angle β , and a constant lateral acceleration $a_n = |\vec{a}_n|$. The degrees of freedom of the model are defined as $\underline{s} = [\delta, \beta, \omega_L, \omega_R]^T$. The goal of the model is to find a quasi-static solution for a given forward velocity v and corner radius R .

2.1. Kinematics

The calculation of the equations of motion starts by defining the velocity components of the center of gravity (CoG) as

$$v_x = v \cos(\beta) \quad v_y = -v \sin(\beta) \quad \omega_z = \frac{v}{R}, \tag{1}$$

where v_x and v_y are respectively the longitudinal and lateral CoG velocity. According to the used multibody dynamics approach, the velocity coordinates are stored in a column \underline{v} such that

$$\vec{v} = \underline{v}^T \underline{\vec{e}} = [v_x \quad v_y \quad 0] \begin{bmatrix} \vec{e}_x \\ \vec{e}_y \\ \vec{e}_z \end{bmatrix}, \tag{2}$$

where \vec{e} represents the column of unit vectors that describe a vehicle-fixed axis system with its origin in the CoG. The same notation is used to define the position of each of the six tires with respect to the CoG as

$$\vec{p}_i = p_i^T \vec{e} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, 6, \quad (3)$$

where p_i is the column containing the position coordinates of tire i . These coordinates depend solely on the vehicle dimensions l_f , l_r , s_1 , s_2 , and Δs . Here, l_f and l_r are the distances between the vehicle CoG and the front and rear axle respectively, and s_1 , s_2 , and Δs define the track widths as indicated in Fig. 1.

The local tire velocity vectors can be expressed in each tire-fixed axis system respectively, according to

$$\underline{v}_i = A(\delta_i) \left(\underline{v} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \omega_z \end{bmatrix} \times \underline{p}_i \right) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, 6, \quad (4)$$

where

$$A(\delta_i) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\delta_i) & \sin(\delta_i) & 0 \\ -\sin(\delta_i) & \cos(\delta_i) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

denotes the direction cosine matrix that rotates the velocity vector from the vehicle-fixed frame to the tire-fixed frame as function of the steer angle δ_i . The front wheel steer angles δ_1 and δ_2 are assumed to be related through the Ackermann steering relation (Kageyama et al., 2014, p. 924),

$$\delta_1 = \tan^{-1} \left(l \left(\frac{l}{\tan \delta} - s_1 \right)^{-1} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \delta_2 = \tan^{-1} \left(l \left(\frac{l}{\tan \delta} + s_1 \right)^{-1} \right) \quad (6)$$

with $l = l_f + l_r$ the wheelbase of the vehicle. Because the rear wheels are not steered, the direction cosine matrices corresponding to these wheels are $A(\delta_3) = A(\delta_4) = A(\delta_5) = A(\delta_6) = I$, where I is the 3×3 unity matrix.

The coordinates of the local velocity vector with respect to the tire-fixed axis system are contained in the column \underline{v}_i . The first and second component of this column are denoted as $v_{x,i}$ and $v_{y,i}$, respectively. From these velocity components, the tire side-slip angle α_i and the longitudinal slip ratio κ_i can be determined;

$$\alpha_i = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{-v_{y,i}}{|v_{x,i}|} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \kappa_i = -\frac{v_{x,i} - r_{e,i} \omega_i}{|v_{x,i}|} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, 6. \quad (7)$$

In these calculations, the effective tire radius $r_{e,i}$ is considered to be linearly dependent on the vertical force $F_{z,i}$ acting on the tire. Furthermore, longitudinal slip of the front tires, which are not driven, is neglected.

2.2. Dynamics

In order to include load transfer both in longitudinal and lateral direction, the CoG accelerations in these directions are expressed respectively as

$$a_x = \sin(\beta) \frac{v^2}{R} \quad a_y = \cos(\beta) \frac{v^2}{R}. \quad (8)$$

Next, the pitch moment M_{pitch} and roll moment M_{roll} are defined:

$$M_{pitch} = -h a_x m \quad M_{roll} = h a_y m \quad (9)$$

with h the CoG height and the m the total vehicle mass. A positive pitch moment M_{pitch} redistributes part of the total vertical force from the rear axle to the front axle. This difference in vertical force is indicated by

$$\Delta F_{z,pitch} = \frac{M_{pitch}}{l_f + l_r}. \quad (10)$$

Similarly, a roll moment results in a difference in the total vertical force between the left and right track of the model. The roll moment distribution k_{dist} determines the distribution of this moment between the front and rear axle. The difference in vertical force between the left and right track is therefore described by

$$\Delta F_{z,front} = k_{dist} \frac{M_{roll}}{2s_1} \quad \Delta F_{z,rear} = (1 - k_{dist}) \frac{M_{roll}}{2s_2}. \quad (11)$$

The total vertical force on each of the tires is a result of the static vertical force plus the effects of the two types of load transfer, resulting in

$$F_{z,1} = \frac{l_r}{2l} m g - \Delta F_{z,front} + \frac{1}{2} \Delta F_{z,pitch} \quad (12a)$$

$$F_{z,2} = \frac{l_r}{2l}mg + \Delta F_{z,front} + \frac{1}{2}\Delta F_{z,pitch} \quad (12b)$$

$$F_{z,3} = F_{z,4} = \frac{l_f}{4l}mg - \frac{1}{2}\Delta F_{z,rear} - \frac{1}{4}\Delta F_{z,pitch} \quad (12c)$$

$$F_{z,5} = F_{z,6} = \frac{l_f}{4l}mg + \frac{1}{2}\Delta F_{z,rear} - \frac{1}{4}\Delta F_{z,pitch} \quad (12d)$$

with g the gravitational acceleration. As can be seen from (12c) and (12d) it is assumed that the vertical load is equal for two tires that are double mounted, e.g. $F_{z,3} = F_{z,4}$.

To model the tires, a simplified version of Pacejka's Magic Formula (Pacejka, 2012, p. 7) is used. The Magic Formula is an established tire model that accurately captures the nonlinear tire behaviour that occurs while taking sharp corners. The input parameters required for this tire model are included in the code (Beckers et al., 2020) and describe typical bus or truck tires. The tire model expresses the longitudinal and lateral tire force, $F_{x,i}$ and $F_{y,i}$ respectively, as function of the slip conditions κ_i and α_i and the vertical tire force $F_{z,i}$:

$$F_{x,i} = f_{MF,x}(\kappa_i, F_{z,i}) + f_{mon,x}(\kappa) \quad \text{and} \quad F_{y,i} = f_{MF,y}(\alpha_i, F_{z,i}) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, 6. \quad (13)$$

The longitudinal force expression in (13) is slightly altered with respect to the original Magic Formula by adding $f_{mon,x}(\kappa)$. This mathematical function is used in other contexts to model mechanical freeplay (Howcroft et al., 2013) and is described by

$$f_{mon,x}(\kappa) = \frac{50000}{\pi} \left(\left(\kappa + \kappa_c \right) \left(\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{-1}{\kappa_e} (\kappa + \kappa_c) \right) + \frac{\pi}{2} \right) + \left(\kappa - \kappa_c \right) \left(\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{\kappa_e} (\kappa - \kappa_c) \right) + \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \right). \quad (14)$$

The function is linear for large slip values ($|\kappa| \gg \kappa_c$) and approximately zero for $-\kappa_c < \kappa < \kappa_c$, where κ_c is chosen 0.6 and the smoothness is determined by $\kappa_e = 0.02$. This addition is made to ensure monotonicity of the longitudinal force with respect to κ and aids the performance of the used Newton scheme, which will be described in Section 2.3. The modified Magic Formula expression for the vertical force is visualised in Fig. 2. Because the final steady-state solution of the model, also indicated in Fig. 2, generally has low slip longitudinal values, it is not affected by the discussed modification.

Before summation, the individual tire forces are transformed back to the vehicle-fixed axis system described by \vec{e} :

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sum F_x \\ \sum F_y \\ \sum F_z \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^6 F_i = \sum_{i=1}^6 A^{-1}(\delta_i) \begin{bmatrix} F_{x,i} \\ F_{y,i} \\ F_{z,i} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

Four equations describe the steady-state solution. First of all, in accordance with the assumption of a constant yaw-rate ω_z , there is a moment equilibrium around the vertical axis:

$$\sum M_z = \sum_{i=1}^6 p_i \times E_i = 0. \quad (16)$$

Secondly, the force equilibrium should hold for both the tangential and normal direction:

Fig. 2. Magic Formula function describing the longitudinal tire force as function of the slip ratio. The function used in this study is adapted to be a monotonic function of the slip ratio. The steady-state solution for $v = 22.5$ km/h and $R = 10$ m, corresponding to results of the inner right rear tire (tire 5) is also indicated.

$$\Sigma F_t = \cos(\beta) \Sigma F_x - \sin(\beta) \Sigma F_y = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\Sigma F_n = \sin(\beta) \Sigma F_x - \cos(\beta) \Sigma F_y = \frac{mv^2}{R}. \quad (18)$$

The last equilibrium equation is a moment equilibrium between the left and right rear wheels. This results from the assumption that a mechanical differential distributes the torque produced by the powertrain evenly and without losses between the left and right wheels:

$$M_L - M_R = 0 \quad \text{with} \quad M_L = (F_{x,3}r_{e,3} + F_{x,4}r_{e,4}) \quad M_R = (F_{x,5}r_{e,5} + F_{x,6}r_{e,6}). \quad (19)$$

2.3. Newton iterations

To find a solution for a given value of v and R , (16)–(19) are to be solved simultaneously for the degrees of freedom $\underline{s} = [\delta, \beta, \omega_L, \omega_R]^T$. In this case, unconstrained adapted Newton iterations (Papalambros and Wilde, 2000) are used to find the solutions numerically. Hereto,

$$\underline{s}_{k+1} = \underline{s}_k + \gamma(-\underline{J}(\underline{s}_k)^{-1}\underline{\varepsilon}(\underline{s}_k)) \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (20)$$

is evaluated repeatedly. In this equation, $\underline{\varepsilon}_k$ is the column containing the errors in the four equilibrium equations in respectively [N] and [Nm] as function of the current degrees of freedom \underline{s}_k . Furthermore, γ is the adapted Newton step size. The matrix \underline{J} represents the Jacobian matrix of $\underline{\varepsilon}_k$ with respect to the degrees of freedom \underline{s}_k and is determined numerically using the central difference approximation. The solution of the linearized single track model at low velocity is used as the starting point for the iterative scheme (Pacejka, 2012);

$$\underline{s}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \tan^{-1}(l/\sqrt{R^2 - l_r}) \\ \tan^{-1}(-l_r/\sqrt{R^2 - l_r}) \\ v/r_e \\ v/r_e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

2.4. Model results for a city bus

Using this model, the tire forces and the work performed by these forces can be calculated for any realistic cornering situation defined by the vehicle velocity v and corner radius R . The model is solved for an exemplary cornering situation of $v = 22.5$ km/h and $R = 10$ m, using typical BEB parameters, as listed in Table 1. The velocity and force vectors of the obtained solution are shown in Fig. 3. From the results of this particular cornering situation, it becomes evident that the side-slip angles differ for the individual tires. Also the vertical forces the tires, shown in Fig. 4, show great variation. Both effects result in different longitudinal and lateral forces being generated by each individual tire.

The force vectors originating from the front tires are rotated with respect to the velocity direction, due to the vehicle side-slip angle and the significant steer-angles. As a result, the lateral tire forces are partially directed in the rearward direction. These tangential rearward components of the lateral tire forces are often referred to as *cornering resistance*. To maintain a steady-state situation, this cornering resistance is countered by a net longitudinal force produced by the rear tires. Therefore, the cornering resistance power P_{cRes} can be calculated according to

$$P_{cRes} = \sum_{i=3}^6 F_{x,i} v_{x,i}, \quad (22)$$

where $F_{x,i}$ and $v_{x,i}$ are the longitudinal tire force and velocity of the respective rear tires.

At the rear tires, additional longitudinal forces exist. Of each set of double rear wheels, the tire closest to the corner center develops a forward force, while the tire furthest from the center generates a smaller rearward force. This effect is caused by the fixed rotational velocity of each set of double wheels and the fact that each wheel has a slightly different radius with respect to the corner

Table 1
Vehicle parameters of a typical BEB.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Vehicle mass (incl. passengers)	m	15000 kg
Wheelbase	l	6 m
Longitudinal CoG position	l_f	3.5 m
CoG height above road	h	1.5 m
Average track width	$2s_1 = 2s_2 + \Delta s$	2 m
Roll moment distribution	k_{dist}	1/4

Fig. 3. Schematic top view of the vehicle and wheels with the solution of the steady-state cornering model for the parameters $v = 22.5 \text{ km/h}$ and $R = 10 \text{ m}$. The dashed line indicates the path of the CoG. Velocity vectors and force vectors are indicated using arrows. The size of the arrows corresponds to the magnitude of the vectors. This figure is directly generated by the MATLAB-script provided in (Beckers et al., 2020).

Fig. 4. Vertical tire force of the steady-state solution for each of the six tires in case $v = 22.5 \text{ km/h}$ and $R = 10 \text{ m}$.

center. This effectively results in additional *tire scrub*, which also results in additional energy losses. The power lost due to this effect can be calculated by multiplying the local slip velocity with the longitudinal tire force:

$$P_{scrub} = \sum_{i=3}^6 F_{x,i} (-v_{x,i} + r_{e,i} \omega_i). \tag{23}$$

Overcoming the cornering resistance force and the tire scrub losses requires additional work, which is ultimately delivered by the powertrain of the vehicle. Using the described model, the work required to overcome each of these effects is determined for varying cornering situations (v, R). Fig. 5 shows the resulting cornering resistance power P_{cRes} and the power lost due to tire scrub P_{scrub} .

The results indicate that both effects vary as function of cornering situation, and are most profound for tight, fast corners. P_{cRes} is

(a) Power losses due to cornering resistance

(b) Power losses due to rear wheel tire scrub

Fig. 5. Resulting energy losses due to cornering resistance (a) and rear wheel tire scrub (b) for a range of vehicle velocities and corner radii. Solutions for high lateral accelerations ($a_y > 0.4g$) are not considered as the vehicle is close to roll over in this region (Beckers et al., 2019).

the more significant effect for the majority of the cornering situations and can reach values of up to 20 kW. P_{scrub} is more relevant for low velocity, small radius situations and can still exceed 1 kW. Therefore, both effects are taken into consideration for further analysis and are together indicated as the *combined cornering losses* P_{loss} , which are equal to the total power requested from the vehicle's motor to overcome the considered losses;

$$P_{loss} = P_{cRes} + P_{scrub} = M_L \omega_L + M_R \omega_R. \quad (24)$$

3. Model validation

In order to verify whether the combined cornering losses predicted by the described cornering model are realistic, dedicated steady-state cornering tests have been conducted with an electric city bus. The goal of the experiment is to correlate the measured energy consumption of the vehicle during a tight cornering situation to the energy consumption as predicted by the cornering model described in Section 2.

3.1. Experimental setup

The experiment was conducted with a two-axle, 12m BEB, fitted with C3 class tires of energy efficiency class D according to EU regulations (European Union Parliament, 2009). Since the test was performed using a specific vehicle, the vehicle parameters of this vehicle are used for the subsequent simulation results. These are slightly different from the parameters described in Table 1, also because the vehicles was largely unladen during the test. The vehicle was equipped with a CAN-logging device to enable the recording of several relevant sensors. Most importantly, all wheel velocities, the steering wheel angle, and the powertrain Direct Current (DC) power consumption were recorded. The test was conducted on a level piece of concrete of 80×360 m. Before start of the tests, the vehicle was driven for approximately 1 hour to reach steady-state temperatures in all powertrain components and tires.

The experiment consists of two parts. First the base power request of the powertrain of the vehicle was established by driving the vehicle in a straight line at various velocities. Secondly, the vehicle was driven in circles with the same velocities, thereby achieving steady-state cornering situations. By comparing the average power request of the powertrain for both situations, the additional power required for cornering can be determined.

3.2. Straight line driving results

The straight line driving power request of the vehicle is determined by driving at a constant velocity in a straight line. This maneuver is conducted multiple times for velocities ranging from 5 km/h to 35 km/h, with intervals of 5 km/h. Results of such a test are displayed in Fig. 6a. These show that during the 120 s measurement the vehicle velocity ranges between 5 km/h and 7 km/h and is not exactly constant. This is mainly due to the absence of a cruise control on the test vehicle and the fact that the powertrain seems to operate at discrete power levels. Therefore, average values for both velocity and powertrain power are obtained by averaging over the 120 s time interval. The same procedure is repeated for multiple vehicle velocities. The duration of the measurement interval is limited by the length of the available driving area. Therefore, tests at higher velocities have shorter durations. The tests are conducted in two directions to average possible slope and wind effects. Due to the presence of significant wind during the test, the directions are

(a) Powertrain power and vehicle velocity during straight line driving.

(b) Average powertrain power as function of velocity.

Fig. 6. Measured average powertrain power as function of vehicle velocity while driving in a straight line. The measurement was performed in two directions, one direction against the wind (headwind) and one direction along the wind direction (tailwind). A third order fit of the measurements is indicated in red.

labeled ‘headwind’ and ‘tailwind’, accordingly. The results are combined in Fig. 6b. These results show that the power consumption increases with velocity and confirm that the average power consumption is slightly higher in the headwind situation. The tests up until 20 km/h are performed twice and show good repeatability.

Also in Fig. 6b a polynomial fit is applied to express the average powertrain power as function of vehicle velocity in the straight line driving situation. The used polynomial is of third order, with coefficients constrained to be positive, in order to represent the power due to rolling resistance (mostly $\propto v$) and aerodynamic resistance ($\propto v^3$). This fit represents the power consumption for straight line driving due to rolling resistance, aerodynamic drag and the internal powertrain losses.

3.3. Cornering results

For the second part of the test, the vehicle was driven at a constant velocity in circles of varying radii. The steer angle was kept constant during each measurement, thereby achieving a steady-state cornering situation. Measurements were performed both clockwise (right-hand turn) and counter-clockwise (left-hand turn) and each measurement lasted approximately 60 s. Again, both vehicle velocity and powertrain power are averaged over each measurement interval.

As the steer angle and the vehicle velocity are controlled during the experiment, the resulting corner radius has to be measured or determined otherwise. In this case, the corner radius is determined from the individual wheel speeds. The vehicle yaw-rate ω_z is calculated from the front wheel velocities by

$$\omega_z = \frac{v_2 - v_1}{2s_1 \cos(\delta)}, \quad (25)$$

where v_1 and v_2 are the velocities of the front left and right wheel, respectively. Furthermore, s_1 is half of the front track width and δ is the average front steer angle, which is derived from the measured steering wheel angle. From the yaw rate, the corner radius R is determined according to

$$R = \frac{v}{\omega_z}, \quad (26)$$

where v is the velocity of the CoG, which is approximated as the unweighted average of the four individual wheel speeds. Experiments were conducted at four different radii, as displayed in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 shows the measured average power request while performing the steady-state cornering maneuver (markers), as well as the straight-line driving power request determined earlier (red). It is evident that the measured power request of the vehicle during cornering is significantly higher than the straight line power request. This difference can reach values of up to 15 kW at higher velocities. Furthermore, based on the measurements there seems to be little difference between data from a left-hand turn and a right-hand turn, indicating that the vehicle is symmetric.

The experimental data of the straight line driving measurements and the results of the cornering model are combined in the black line in Fig. 7. For the corner radii 7.5 m, 11 m, and 25.5 m the model results seem in good agreement with the measured power consumption. The model appears to predict the increased power consumption during cornering accurately, both for low velocities and for higher velocities. However, when analysing the results for the minimal corner radius, $R = 7.5$ m, the measurements at $v = 20$ km/h fall far below the predicted energy consumption. The tests performed in this situation show very high lateral accelerations (near 4 m/s^2) and are on the edge of the cornering capabilities of the vehicle. This is also indicated by velocity peaks in the individual tire velocities, shown in Fig. 8a. These peaks indicate a loss of traction of the outer rear wheels and a subsequent interaction of the vehicle’s electronic stability control system. Because these measurements are not steady-state, they are treated as outliers for the remainder of the analysis.

The difference between the measured and modeled power is visualised in detail in Fig. 8b. This figure shows that generally, the model underestimates the increase of the measured power request. Only between 15 km/h and 26 km/h, the model overestimates the power request in some instances. On average, the deviation between model and measurement is 0.8 kW, which corresponds to approximately 0.5% of the maximum powertrain power of the considered vehicle. Even though the error of the model is not completely random, suggesting some structural deviation, the overall error is very small. The deviation could be caused by the fact that the tire parameters used are only estimates and are not matched to the exact tires that were used during the experiments. However, the power estimated by the model tends to be on the conservative side, resulting in slightly lower values than those that were measured.

In general, the model shows a good correlation with the measurement results for these relatively tight cornering situations, up until a radius of 25.5 m. Larger corner radii could not be tested due to the limited size of the available test area. As the model properly describes the most tight cornering situations it is assumed to be valid for larger corner radii as well.

4. Cornering losses on real bus routes

It has been established that the combined cornering losses are significant for fast, sharp corners. Therefore, the question remains whether a BEB encounters these type of cornering situations often during normal driving. To provide an answer, real-world bus fleet data is analysed. Four BEBs, each driving a different route on different locations were monitored for one day, thus collecting 62 h of data. Of each vehicle, GPS-position, wheel-based vehicle speed, and powertrain power consumption were measured with a sampling rate of 0.5 Hz. During the measurements, the vehicles were normally operated as part of a public transport fleet.

(a) Corner radius: 7.5 m.

(b) Corner radius: 11 m.

(c) Corner radius: 18 m.

(d) Corner radius: 25.5 m.

Fig. 7. Average powertrain power as function of vehicle velocity as measured during steady-state cornering. Both measurements for right-hand turns and left-hand turns are shown. The straight line driving power and the power as predicted by the cornering model are also indicated. Data of four different corner radii is shown: 7.5 m (a), 11 m (b), 18 m (c), and 25.5 m (d). Outliers are marked gray.

(a) Individual wheel velocities at $R = 7.5$ m.

(b) Difference between measurement and model.

Fig. 8. Detail of the recorded wheel speed velocities during one of the measurements (a). Difference between measured and modeled average powertrain power request for all different corner radii and different velocities.

Fig. 9. Schematic view of the corner radius calculation based on GPS-coordinates (a) and the resulting corner curvature (b), indicated by the length of the black lines.

Because a steering wheel angle sensor is not present on the vehicles, the radius of the turns is estimated from the GPS-signal. Preprocessing of the signal is performed by removing GPS-points with little intermediate distance and by subsequently applying a Savitzky-Golay low-pass filter (Savitzky and Golay, 1964) to remove signal content with a high spatial frequency. These steps minimize the influence of GPS-sensor noise in the estimated corner radii. After preprocessing, the corner radius is calculated as the radius of circle circumscribing the triangle spanned by a GPS-coordinate n and its two neighbouring points $n - 1$ and $n + 1$, as indicated in Fig. 9a. In Fig. 9b, the resulting corner radius is visualized as a curvature [1/m] for a section of the analysed route. The results show that the algorithm correctly identifies corners of different curvature.

The resulting radii can be displayed as function of the vehicle velocity, as shown in Fig. 10. Additionally, the combined cornering losses P_{loss} as defined in (24) are included in the figure. While calculating P_{loss} as displayed here, vehicle parameters are used that exactly represent the vehicles under consideration. These parameter values vary only slightly from the typical values mentioned in Table 1. The vehicles are assumed to be 50% laden. The results of four different routes are presented: a city route, a city route that also includes rural driving to a nearby suburban area, a purely rural route between several small villages, and a rural route that includes a section of highway.

Overall, the results show that all kinds of corner radii can be observed, ranging from sharp corners $R \approx 10$ m to straight line driving. When analysing the city route specifically, as displayed in Fig. 10a, it becomes evident that the corner radius is positively correlated to the vehicle velocity. Therefore, smaller corner radii of $R < 50$ m are only reached at lower vehicle velocities of $v < 30$ km/h. A similar trend is visible in Fig. 10b, which shows the results for a city/rural route. In this case, the distribution of corner radii is wider. When analysing a rural route, as displayed in Fig. 10c, velocities up to 80 km/h are reached, which is the extra-urban speed limit. Lastly, in the route containing mainly rural and highway driving, shown in Fig. 10d, the vehicle regularly drives either roughly 50 km/h or its maximum velocity of 80 km/h.

In the high velocity region of Fig. 10c, a pattern becomes visible in the distribution of determined corner radii. This is a side-effect of the limited resolution of the available GPS-data and the fact that the analyzed route is largely aligned with the WGS84-coordinate grid used to describe the GPS measurements. Combined, these effects result in an erroneous discretization of the corner radii at higher velocities. As this effect only occurs at large radii, the influence on the energy consumption is considered to be small.

The total energy lost due to the described cornering effects is assessed. Hereto, the nonlinear steady-state cornering model is evaluated for each of the measured cornering situations as displayed in Fig. 10. Integrating the resulting power gives the energy loss due to cornering resistance E_{cRes} and tire scrub E_{scrub} . This energy is compared to the measured total energy consumption of the powertrain of the vehicle E_{tot} in Table 2. This E_{tot} is obtained by integrating the recorded DC voltage and current from the powertrain inverter, while also taking the limited battery efficiency into account.

The comparison reveals that, in general, the scrub energy E_{scrub} is relatively small compared to the cornering resistance energy E_{cRes} . This is to be expected, as it was already observed from the model results in Fig. 5 that the powerloss due to this effect is comparably small. Nevertheless, tire scrub constitutes approximately 9% of the combined cornering losses.

When analysing the specific trips, it becomes clear that the contribution of the cornering losses with respect to the total energy consumption depends on the type of route. Whereas the contribution of cornering losses is relatively minor for the rural/highway route, the effect is more profound in case of the city route and the city/rural route. A possible cause is found in a combination of the street layout and the local velocity legislation. The rural/highway route contains many straight roads, while the average vehicle velocity, and thus also the total powertrain power consumption, is relatively high. This reduces the impact of cornering losses. In contrast, the city/rural route was mainly driven around a city center that contains many curved roads. Additionally, this specific route contained a high number of roundabouts, on average one every 1.8 km, increasing the influence of the considered effects. Averaged over the considered routes, the combined cornering losses compose more than 3% of the powertrain energy consumption.

Fig. 10. Combined cornering losses calculated by the model as function of vehicle velocity and corner radius. Recorded data from electric buses operating in the field indicate the occurrence of these situations. Data of four different routes are shown: city (a), city/rural (b), rural (c), and rural/highway (d). Solutions for lateral accelerations of $a_y > 0.4g$ are not considered as the vehicle is close to roll-over in these situations.

Table 2

Calculated cornering resistance energy E_{cRes} and tire scrub energy E_{Scrub} with respect to the total powertrain energy E_{tot} for several electric bus routes.

Route	E_{tot} [kWh]	$\frac{E_{cRes}}{E_{tot}}$ [%]	$\frac{E_{Scrub}}{E_{tot}}$ [%]	$\frac{E_{cRes} + E_{Scrub}}{E_{tot}}$ [%]
City	139.7	2.82	0.39	3.21
City/Rural	131.9	5.32	0.43	5.75
Rural	150.5	2.11	0.18	2.29
Rural/Highway	393.2	1.25	0.07	1.32
Average over routes	203.8	2.86	0.27	3.14

5. Discussion and limitations

A nonlinear steady-state cornering model for a BEB has been developed. Although the model contains many nonlinear effects, such as individual, large steer angles, load transfer, and a Magic Formula tire model, not all possible physics are included. The current tire model does not include combined slip, turn slip, or camber. The influence of these phenomena is expected to be small, since the corner radius R is large compared to the tire width (turn slip) and the longitudinal tire forces are small (combined slip). Furthermore, the influence of camber angles on the lateral force is neglected. Also, while load transfer due to the elevated center of gravity is included in the model, body roll is not considered. Nevertheless, the validation show a close resemblance between model and measurement. Therefore, it can be concluded that the considered level of detail in the model is sufficient for the purposes considered

here.

The model aims to quantify the additional forces involved when cornering the vehicle. Therefore, conventional road-load forces, such as aerodynamic drag or rolling resistance, are not considered in the model. The effect that these forces might have on the slip conditions of the tires is neglected. Consequently, the results presented here do not allow for any relations between the presented cornering losses and the rolling resistance properties of the tires. Furthermore, the energy consumption due to deceleration into the corner and acceleration out of the corner are not included in the study presented here.

In de impact assessment presented in Section 4, many of the vehicle parameters are known accurately for the considered vehicles. One exception is the loading condition of the vehicles. For city buses this can change throughout the day, or even throughout a single trip. The vehicle mass is therefore based on the assumption that the vehicles are 50% laden on average. In order to get an indication of the influence the mass variation might have the final result, the expression for the cornering resistance power derived from the linear bicycle model (Kobayashi et al., 2017; Ikezawa et al., 2019) can be used;

$$P_{CRes,lin} = \left(\left[\frac{l_r^2}{2l^2} \frac{1}{C_{F\alpha,f}} + \frac{l_f^2}{2l^2} \frac{1}{C_{F\alpha,r}} \right] m^2 a_y^2 \right) v = \left[\frac{l_r^2}{2l^2} \frac{1}{C_{F\alpha,f}} + \frac{l_f^2}{2l^2} \frac{1}{C_{F\alpha,r}} \right] \frac{m^2 v^5}{R^2}, \quad (27)$$

where $C_{F\alpha,f}$ and $C_{F\alpha,r}$ are the front and rear cornering stiffness respectively. The cornering stiffness is a tire property describing the lateral force a tire generates per unit of side-slip angle. As a first approximation, the cornering stiffness is a linear function of the normal load on the tires, and thus of the vehicle mass, i.e. $C_{F\alpha} \propto m$ (Pacejka, 2012). Therefore, it can be concluded that the cornering resistance power, which is the most significant of the combined cornering losses, increases linearly with vehicle mass:

$$P_{CRes} \propto m. \quad (28)$$

Nevertheless, the used vehicle mass m is considered to be accurate enough on average. Only approximately 15% of the mass is determined by the passenger loading, and the remainder is vehicle weight, which is accurately known.

Results from a specific cornering situation show that both cornering resistance and tire scrub of the rear double tires cause additional cornering losses. The former of these effects is much more profound. Therefore, cornering losses are also significant for heavy-duty vehicles not equipped with double rear tires. Furthermore, the detailed results in Figs. 3 and 4 show the variation in side slip angles and vertical tire forces between the individual tires. This emphasizes the importance of using a nonlinear double-track model to accurately simulate these tight cornering situations with a heavy-duty vehicle. If only a linear bicycle model were used, the differences in tire load, local velocity, and side-slip angle between the left and right side of the vehicle would not have been modeled in sufficient detail. Also the additional effect of tire scrub can only be studied in case the track width of the vehicle is not neglected.

Recordings from four real-world BEB routes are analysed. From recorded CAN-bus data, the corner radius could only be determined through analysis of the GPS-trace. Even though the analysis shows plausible results, some deviations are expected due to the noise and limited resolution of the considered GPS-sensor. These errors are expected to not introduce any bias and therefore still results in a realistic corner radius distribution. Lastly, it is assumed a realistic cornering situation can be represented by a sequence of different steady-state results generated by the model.

The final results show that the cornering effects described here account on average for 3.1% of the powertrain energy of the considered vehicle. It is also shown that the combined cornering losses can momentarily reach values of several kW's. These results seem to be in accordance with previous research by (Maclaurin, 2008), who simulated vehicles of similar dimensions, and (Gyenes et al., 1979), who concluded that for long freight trucks the cornering losses would be bound to roughly 3% of the total energy consumption. Our results indicate that for BEBs driving in a city environment, the relative contribution of these cornering losses can even be as high as 5.8%. Considering the limited available energy of most BEBs, and electric vehicles in general, it seems that cornering losses have a significant impact on the driving range and should not be neglected. In contrast, literature shows that in many energy consumption prediction analyses cornering of the vehicle is not considered. It is likely that in these cases the cornering losses are implicitly included as part of the rolling resistance. According Vepsäläinen et al., 2018, Fig. 1, approximately 40% of the powertrain energy is ascribed to rolling resistance. Therefore, the indicated share of 3.1% cornering losses corresponds to a change in rolling resistance of approximately 7.75%.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, the additional energy losses that occur due to tire slip while cornering are assessed using a nonlinear steady-state cornering model. From the model, *cornering resistance* losses and *tire scrub* losses from the rear double tires are identified, where the latter are less significant yet still relevant. The outcome of the model matches the additional power consumption as measured during full scale steady-state cornering tests and the model shows an average deviation of only 0.8kW, i.e., approximately 0.5% of the maximum power of the vehicle.

Using the validated model, various routes are analysed. By comparing the simulated cornering losses with the measured energy consumption of the vehicle powertrain, it is shown that the cornering losses on average constitute 3.1% of the powertrain energy consumption. The effect varies depending on route type. While cornering losses are less profound for rural or highway routes, the contribution of these losses can reach values of up to 5.8% for routes in a city environment. Considering the fact that BEBs are currently mostly deployed in city centers, it seems relevant to take the described effects into consideration in the development of accurate range prediction algorithms. Therefore, a topic of future research is the inclusion of the described effects in a physics-based energy consumption prediction model for electric city buses.

Due to the employed multibody approach in the model description, the wheel configuration of the modeled vehicle can be changed easily. Consequently, different types of heavy-duty vehicles can be simulated by adapting the parameterized wheel locations and the vehicle parameters. Therefore, the model presented here, and for which the code is provided in (Beckers et al., 2020), can be used to research the described cornering losses for different types of vehicles, such as electric semi trailer-trucks.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

C.J.J. Beckers: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing - original draft. **I.J.M. Besselink:** Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **H. Nijmeijer:** Resources, Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <https://doi.org/10.4121/uuid:e6560568-4203-43c5-9fdb-a91bc5e2cee4>.

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